

Exploration of the Rima Bode Region. H. Hiesinger¹, C. H. van der Bogert¹, S. Mikolajewski¹, A. Wedler², R. Jaumann³, U. Mall⁴, J.W. Head⁵, M. Anand⁶, B. Jolliff⁷, P. Pinet⁸, L. Xiao⁹, M. Ivanov¹⁰, B. Gundlach¹¹, N. Schmitz¹², M. Schweitzer¹³, C. Bergemann-Mecucci¹³, A. Jaime¹³, M.C. DeSanctis¹⁴, S. Besse¹⁵, M. Massironi¹⁶, I. Crawford¹⁷, E. Hauber¹², A. Frigeri¹⁴, R. Tartese¹⁸, F. Rull¹⁹, F. McDonald²⁰, J. Carpenter²⁰. ¹Inst. für Planetologie, Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität, Wilhelm-Klemm-Str. 10, 48149 Münster, Germany (hiesinger@uni-muenster.de); ²DLR-Inst. of Robotics and Mechatronics; ³Freie Univ. Berlin; ⁴Max-Planck Inst. für Sonnensystemforschung; ⁵Dept. Earth, Env. & Planet. Sci., Brown Univ.; ⁶The Open Univ., UK; ⁷Washington Univ. St. Louis; ⁸IRAP, CNRS/CNES/Toulouse Univ.; ⁹CUG-Wuhan Univ.; ¹⁰Vernadsky Institute; ¹¹Univ. Braunschweig; ¹²DLR-Inst. für Planetenforschung; ¹³OHB System AG; ¹⁴INAF-IAPS; ¹⁵Aurora Technology; ¹⁶Univ. di Padova; ¹⁷Univ. London Birbeck, ¹⁸Univ. Manchester, ¹⁹Univ. de Valladolid, ²⁰ESA-ESTEC

Introduction: Returning to the Moon within the next decade is the objective of many space-faring nations, including, the US, China, Japan, India, UAE, and Europe. In this context, landed robotic precursor missions with landers capable of bringing up to several tons of equipment and scientific instruments to the lunar surface are planned. Most plans focus on landing sites close to the lunar south pole, particularly to explore and potentially utilize the expected water ice deposits in the permanently shaded regions (PSRs) on the floors of craters. Potential use of these deposits could be the production of fuel for further exploration of the Solar System or the consumption by astronauts staying for extended periods on the Moon in a lunar station.

Landing near the south pole of the Moon is challenging in many respects, including illumination conditions and decent orbit. In addition, it is difficult to access PSRs as they have very low temperatures and low lighting conditions and frequently occur at the base of steep slopes that can not easily be navigated with rovers and even less by humans. Although the scientific questions about volatiles on the Moon are highly interesting and relevant, there are many other equally important questions that can be addressed at less challenging landing sites. For example, impact processes, effusive and explosive volcanic processes, regolith processes and their histories as well as the testing of ISRU capabilities can be studied outside the polar regions.

Here we present a scenario that might be technologically less challenging and might be accomplished at lower costs than a lunar polar landing. After a thorough global search of particularly interesting and comprehensive geology, we selected the Rima Bode region as a candidate landing site. With several compositionally different mare units, as well as pyroclastic deposits [e.g., 1, 2] and a cone-like structure, this region offers unique opportunities to study lunar volcanism. The area is also affected by ray material from Copernicus crater, ejecta from Eratosthenes crater, and exhibits highland material and ejecta from the Imbrium basin [e.g., 1, 2]. Hence, the proposed landing region is geologically extremely complex and permits studying several key science questions concerning early crustal differentiation, volcanic history and evolution, impact history,

and the potential for utilizing pyroclastic deposits for the extraction of volatiles and other potential lunar resources (i.e., ISRU). All geologically diverse units can be accessed with a rover traverse less than ~150-200 km long, slopes less than ~7°, and low rock abundances.

The large payload mass of ESA's Argonaut lander makes it the optimal tool for delivering a rover to the lunar surface that is capable of travelling 10s -100s of kilometers, has night survival capabilities, and carries a comprehensive suite of instruments (e.g., LIBS, Raman, IR-spectrometer, multispectral stereo cameras, GPR) to characterize and pre-select interesting samples. We also propose to continuously operate certain instruments while roving. For example, a continuously operated ground-penetrating radar would yield information on the sub-surface regolith structure and an IR-spectrometer would produce mineralogical/compositional profiles along rover traverses [3].

We propose to equip the lander with several instruments, including a geophysical package (e.g., seismometer, heat flow probe, laser retroreflector, etc.). These instruments would benefit from a stable platform and could acquire long-term stable measurements. In addition, geochemical analyses of samples (e.g., in situ radiometric age determination with a laser ablation resonance ionization mass spectrometer [4]) could be performed on the lander and/or the rover. ISRU technology demonstrations are also planned for the lander. Our major science goal with the proposed lander/rover mission concept, is to comprehensively study geologic processes such as lunar volcanism and impact cratering with respect to timing, spatial distribution, composition, mineralogy, structures, eruption styles, volumes, and ISRU potential.

An ESA topical team of lunar scientists evaluated the scientific potential of several candidate landing sites (e.g., Ina D, Copernicus and Tsiolkovsky craters, and a long traverse across Mare Imbrium [e.g., 5-7] on the basis of scientific merits, technological aspects, novelty, and feasibility. Among these landing sites, Rima Bode ranked very high, because of its broad scientific potential and the relatively low technical risks.

In order to study the potential of the Rima Bode landing site in detail, we produced a high-resolution geologic map of the area [8], which provides an excellent basis for more in-depth investigations of the area, including the selection of a landing site and the detailed traverse planning. The new geologic map is an improvement over the existing LAC map of the Mare Vaporum quadrangle [9] in that it distinguishes, for example, among several mare basalt units and enabled us to perform crater size-frequency distribution (CSFD) measurements for some of the

key geological units in order to derive absolute model ages (AMAs) for the mapped units [e.g., 10, 11]. The ages of volcanic deposits, determined via CSFDs and/or radiometric and exposure ages are crucial to reconstruct the thermal evolution of the Moon [e.g., 12, 13]. In addition, the Rima Bode region also contains ray material and ejecta material from Copernicus and Eratosthenes craters, respectively. Determining the exact ages of these two craters is relevant for our accurate understanding of the global lunar stratigraphy [e.g., 14].

Fig. 1: New geologic map of the Rima Bode region [15]

On the basis of our study, we find that the Rima Bode region not only appears to be safe for landing but is also scientifically very interesting. In particular, compared to polar regions, access to the surface and operating equipment on the surface (e.g., a rover and instruments) might be much easier as commanding can be accomplished by direct and uninterrupted communication with Earth. Slopes are gentle, rock abundance is low, and most importantly, temperatures are much less challenging than close to the poles. We assume that the reduced technological complexity will be reflected in the overall costs and the time frame in which such a mission could be accomplished. Scientifically, the landing area might hold key information to better understand processes and products related to volcanism and impact cratering and, hence, the thermal evolution of the Moon. We believe that many science priorities stated in various reports [e.g., 16] can be addressed by landing in the Rima Bode region. On top, the pyroclastic material is particularly suitable for testing various ISRU techniques in preparation for a future human lunar outpost. Hence, an innovative lander/rover mission delivered to this part of the lunar surface could achieve major scientific and technological advances with only small risks. Our mission concept offers a variety of inherent descscope options should future studies reveal technological or budgetary chal-

lenges that can not be overcome within the desired temporal framework of the mission. For example, with a clever landing site selection and traverse planning, many of the objectives could be accomplished while it might be possible to reduce the distance the rover has to travel [17]. Given the distance the rover can travel, certain scientific stops along the traverses might be reachable whereas others will not. This will undoubtedly affect the selection (i.e., reduction) of instruments necessary to address the scientific questions as well as operations and its related costs. From a public outreach point of view, it should not be underestimated that the landing site is always in “plain view” from Earth, allowing amateur astronomers and lay persons to “see” the landing site.

Conclusions: In summary, on the basis of landing site safety and accessibility, available technological capabilities, overall costs, public outreach aspects, and primarily the extraordinary scientific potential, Rima Bode should be considered as a potential site for the first ESA-led landing on the Moon.

References: [1] Spudis and Richards (2018) LLW2018-21; [2] Hiesinger et al. (2021) LPSC 52, 1485; [3] Head and Wilson (2020) Geophys. Res. Lett. 47; [4] Anderson et al. (2015), Rapid Comm. Mass Spectrom. 29; [5] Massironi et al. (2021) ELS; [6] Besse et al. (2022) ELS; [7] Hauber et al. (2022) ELS; [8] Mikolajewski et al. (2023) LPSC 54; [9] Wilhelms (1968), LAC 59, USGS [10] Mikolajewski et al. (2024) LPSC 55; [11] Hiesinger et al. (2022) LPSC 53; [12] Wieczorek et al. (2006) Rev. Min. Geochem. 60; [13] Ziethe et al. (2009), Planet. Space Sci. 57; [14] Hiesinger and Tanaka (2020) Geological Time Scales, Elsevier; [15] Mikolajewski et al. (2025) in preparation; [16] NAC (2007); [17] Hiesinger et al. (2021) LPSC 52.